

NOTES

ion and 4×10^{-3} moles of salicyloylhydrazide were taken in 25 ml of 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol. The pH of the solution was maintained at 3.2 by using sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid. The absorbance was measured at different wavelengths against reagent blank prepared under identical conditions. The complex was found to have maximum absorbance at 490 nm.

To study the effect of time 4×10^{-3} moles of salicyloylhydrazide and 8×10^{-4} moles of Fe(III) ion were taken in 25.0 ml of 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at pH 3.2. The absorbance was measured after regular intervals of time. No change in the absorbance of the solution was observed in about 4 hrs but after this the absorbance decreased slowly.

A series of solutions containing 1 ml of 1×10^{-3} M metal and varying amounts of ligand were prepared. The volume was made 25.0 ml in 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at pH 3.2 in each case. The absorbance was measured against reagent blank at 490 nm. It was observed that the optical density becomes practically constant when about 25 times molar excess of ligand was present.

Composition of the complex :

The nature and composition of the complex was studied by method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁵, Job's method of continuous variation⁶, mole ratio method⁷ and slope ratio method⁸. All the results confirmed the metal to ligand ratio as 1:2 in the complex.

From the absorbance at various concentrations of Fe^{3+} per ml of the solution it was observed that Beer's law is obeyed upto 8 μg of Fe^{3+} per ml of solution.

Effect of the presence of other ions :

A large number of standard solutions containing anions and cations were prepared. The effect of these ions on the absorbance of the complex of Fe(III) with salicyloylhydrazide was studied. It was found that the addition of solutions containing Ag^+ , Sn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , In^{3+} , ZrO^{2+} , CNS^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and AsO_4^{3-} interfered in the formation of the complex. The solution containing Be^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Mg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Th^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , CO_3^{2-} , CH_3COO^- , NO_3^- , F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , IO_3^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, SO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} and tartarate ions did not interfere in the reaction.

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New Zinc(II) Complexes with the Schiff Bases Derived from Salicylaldehyde or Substituted Salicylaldehyde and Orthoaminobenzylalcohol

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THE structure of N-alkylsalicylaldimines embodies several key molecular features common to pyridoxal mediated reactions and N-alkylsalicylaldimines are chemical prototypes of pyridoxal and the B₆ vitamins. The study of coordination complexes of N-alkylsalicylaldimines is of biochemical and biophysical interest. We report in this note the synthesis and characterisation of new zinc(II) complexes with the Schiff bases (I) derived from salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 3, 5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde and orthoaminobenzylalcohol. Although there has been considerable research interest

I.R = H, 5-chloro, 5-bromo, 5-nitro, 3,5-dichloro and 5,6-benzo.

on the coordination complexes of Schiff bases with common metal ions like Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{3+} etc., very little work has been done on the Schiff base complexes of zinc(II)^{1,2}.

Experimental

The metal content was determined by titrating with EDTA using Eriochrome Black-T as an indicator³ after igniting the complex to ZnO and converting it to ZnSO_4 . Carbon and hydrogen analyses were done by Ciba Geigy Research Centre, Bombay. The nitrogen analyses were done microanalytically. The conductance measurements were carried out in methanol with the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE, MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND IR DATA OF ZINC(II) COMPLEXES WITH TRIDENTATE DIBASIC SCHIFF BASES^{a, b}

Complex	Colour	M. W. Found (Calcd.)	Zn	Found (Calcd.) %			ΔM mhos mole ⁻¹ cm ²	$\nu(C=N)$ complex (ligand)	$\nu(C-O)$ phenolic complex (ligand)	$\nu(C-O)$ alcoholic complex (ligand)
Zn(sal-orthoaminobenzylalcohol).H ₂ O	Lemon yellow	316 (308)	20.69 (21.20)	52.18 (54.48)	3.99 (4.22)	4.65 (4.54)	8.1	1605 (1615)	1535 (1530)	1170 (1190)
Zn(5-chlorosal-orthoaminobenzylalcohol).H ₂ O	Pale yellow	344 (343)	19.41 (19.06)	47.09 (48.99)	4.30 (3.50)	3.85 (4.08)	7.4	1610 (1620)	1525 (1520)	1185 (1225)
Zn(5-bromosal-orthoaminobenzylalcohol).H ₂ O	Lemon yellow	391 (387)	16.16 (16.87)	42.39 (43.37)	4.36 (3.10)	3.40 (3.61)	5.9	1610 (1620)	1525 (1515)	1165 (1200)
Zn(5-nitrosal-orthoaminobenzylalcohol).H ₂ O	Yellow	347 (353)	17.91 (18.50)	49.28 (47.54)	3.41 (3.40)	8.08 (7.92)	2.7	1605 (1615)	1555 (1550)	1230 (1240)
Zn(3,5-dichlorosal-orthoaminobenzylalcohol).H ₂ O	Light yellow	362 (377)	17.23 (17.32)	46.42 (44.52)	3.13 (2.91)	3.54 (3.71)	10.5	1615 (1630)	1535 (1510)	1180 (1200)
Zn(hydrox-orthoaminobenzylalcohol).H ₂ O	Brownish yellow	334 (358)	17.94 (18.24)	58.41 (60.27)	4.18 (4.19)	3.77 (3.91)	10.7	1615 (1620)	1535 (1530)	1180 (1215)

(a) Abbreviations : sal = salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosal = 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosal = 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosal = 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 3,5-dichlorosal = 3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde and hydrox = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

(b) All ir bands in cm⁻¹.

help of a Tosbnival Conductivity Bridge (Model LO1-02A) and a dip type cell calibrated with aqueous KCl solutions. Molecular weights of the compounds were determined by the Rast method and diphenyl was used as the solvent⁴. The ir spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using Perkin Elmer 257 infrared spectrophotometer calibrated with polystyrene. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the standard.

General method of syntheses of ligands :

An ethanolic solution of orthoaminobenzylalcohol (0.60 g, 0.005 mole in 10 ml) was added to an ethanolic solution of salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde (0.005 mole in 10 ml). The resulting solution was refluxed on a waterbath for 20 min and as a result a yellow or orange solution was obtained. After partial evaporation of the solvent under a fan the solid compound separated and this was suction filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

General method of synthesis of complexes :

An ethanolic solution of salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde and orthoaminobenzylalcohol (0.005 mole each in 10-20 ml) was treated with an ethanolic solution of Zn(CH₃COO)₂.2H₂O (1.2 g, 0.005 mole in 10 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr on a waterbath. The solid compound was obtained after partial evaporation of the solvent under a fan. This was suction filtered, washed with cold ethanol, recrystallized from ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Yield, 55-65%. The complexes are insoluble in water and soluble in methanol and ethanol.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results indicate that the complexes have the formula Zn(AAA)H₂O (where AAAH₂ = tridentate dibasic Schiff base ligand with ONO donor set). The ir spectra of the complexes are consistent with the presence of coordinated water⁵, the $\nu(OH)$ stretch occurring at around 3000 (br) cm⁻¹. The complexes do not decompose or lose weight on heating at 120° for hours indicating that water is not lost at this temperature and that water is coordinated to Zn. A strong band around 1615-1630 cm⁻¹ in the free ligands is attributable to the $\nu(C=N)$ stretch. In complexes there occurs a shift of this band towards lower frequency region (5-15 cm⁻¹)⁷. This shift to lower frequency region clearly suggests that the azomethine nitrogen atom is co-ordinated to the metal ion. A strong band observed in the range 1510-1540 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the free ligand is assigned to the $\nu(C-O)$ phenolic stretch⁷. In the complexes this band shifts to the higher frequency by 5-25 cm⁻¹. This shift to higher frequency is due to the maintenance of a ring current arising from electron delocalisation in the chelate ring. A strong band in the range 1190-1240 cm⁻¹ is assigned to $\nu(C-O)$ alcoholic stretch in the free ligands⁸. On chelation this band is shifted towards lower frequency region indicating the coordination through the alcoholic oxygen atom of the ligands. The ir, analytical data and the valence requirement of the metal ion clearly indicate tridentate dibasic behaviour of the Schiff bases (I). The complexes are non-electrolytes in methanol. The molecular weight measurements indicate monomeric nature of the complexes. The complexes are diamagnetic as expected for a 3d¹⁰ system. The complexes are four coordinated and a tetrahedral struc-

ture with sp^3 hybridization is suggested to these complexes.

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Titrimetric Determination of Osmium(VIII) and Iridium(IV) with Iron(II)

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ALTHOUGH quite a few titrimetric methods are available for the determination of osmium(VIII) and iridium(IV) almost all of them suffer from one disadvantage or the other; while some of them are cumbersome others are not sufficiently accurate. We have now developed more satisfactory titrimetric methods for the determination of these ions using iron(II) as reductimetric reagent in phosphoric acid medium.

Experimental

Determination of osmium(VIII) :

The titrimetric methods reported so far for the determination of osmium are based mainly on the reduction of osmium(VIII) to lower oxidation states using suitable reductants like iodide¹, thiosulphate², hydrochloric acid¹, titanium(III)¹, chromium(II)^{1,2}, bismuth¹, hexacyanoferrate(II)³ and iron(II) in alkaline medium in presence of mannitol or triethanolamine⁴. We now propose an accurate titrimetric method for the

determination of osmium(VIII) using iron(II) as a reductimetric reagent in phosphoric acid medium.

Reagents : An approximately 0.0025M solution of osmium(VIII) in 0.5M sodium hydroxide was prepared from osmic acid (Johnson Matthey Chemicals Ltd., London) and its strength determined¹. An approximately 0.01M solution of iron(II) was prepared and standardised in the usual way. 0.1% aqueous solutions of methylene blue and thionine were used as indicators. E. Merck, GR, Syrupy phosphoric acid (85%) was employed throughout the study.

Procedure : Enough syrupy phosphoric acid was taken in a 150 ml beaker so that the overall concentration of phosphoric acid was at least 9M (60% v/v) towards the end-point and the beaker was kept in ice-cold water. When the acid in the beaker was cooled sufficiently, an aliquot of osmium(VIII) solution (2-10 ml) was transferred into the beaker followed by 3 drops of methylene blue or thionine indicator. The contents of the beaker were titrated with iron(II) in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide, stirring the solution using a magnetic stirrer. (Care should be taken to see that the temperature of the solution being titrated does not exceed 25° as otherwise volatilisation of osmium occurs to some extent.) The end point was indicated by the disappearance of the blue colour of the dye. An indicator correction of 0.1 ml of 0.01M iron(II) was found to be necessary.

The accuracy of this method (range 1-5 mg of osmium) was found to be $\pm 0.8\%$. When ten samples, each containing 2.38 mg of osmium, were analysed the average and standard deviations were found to be : 2.37 mg, 0.013 mg (thionine); 2.37 mg, 0.014 mg (methylene blue).

Determination of iridium(IV) :

Most of the existing titrimetric methods for the estimation of iridium are based either on the reduction of iridium(IV) to iridium(III) or on the oxidation of iridium(III) to iridium(IV), using suitable redox reagents. The reductimetric reagents used in the determination of iridium(IV) are iron(II)^{1,5}, titanium(III)¹, tin(II)⁶, copper(I)¹, iodide¹, hexacyanoferrate(II)^{1,7}, ascorbic acid¹ and hydroquinone¹. Permanganate¹ appears to be the only oxidimetric reagent used for the estimation of iridium(III). We now report a new titrimetric method for the determination of iridium(IV) with iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium using both potentiometric and visual end-point methods.

Reagents : An approximately 0.01M solution of iridium(IV) was prepared by dissolving the required amount of sodium hexachloroiridate(IV) (Johnson Matthey Chemicals Ltd., London) in 0.5M hydrochloric acid and standardised¹. Solid sodium hexachloroiridate(III) was prepared as suggested by Poulsen and Garner⁸. From this solid an approximately 0.01M aqueous solution of iridium(III) was prepared and standardised¹. 0.1% solution of the indicators were prepared as usual.